

**A NEED OF DRAMATIC ARTS EDUCATION IS AN IMPORTANT MEANS
OF DEVELOPING PERSONALITY OF THE STUDENTS**

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“All the world's a stage, and all the men and women merely players; they have their exits and their entrances. — William Shakespeare

Introduction

"The future of our nation depends on our ability to create-and to be creative. During the coming decades our most important national resources will be human resources. If our nation is to continue to meet the challenges of the future, today's schools need to develop creative leaders."

Dramatic arts education is an important means of stimulating creativity in problem solving. It can challenge students' perceptions about their world and about themselves. Dramatic exploration can provide students with an outlet for emotions, thoughts, and dreams that they might not otherwise have means to express. A student can, if only for a few moments, become another, explore a new role, try out and experiment with various personal choices and solutions to very real problems-problems from their own life, or problems faced by characters in literature or historical figures. This can happen in a safe atmosphere, where actions and consequences can be examined, discussed, and in a very real sense experienced without the dangers and pitfalls that such experimentation would obviously lead to in the "real" world. This is perhaps the most important reason for dramatic arts in schools.

Important of Drama in Education

There is a lot of established research about the positive influences from drama, theatre and the performing arts, especially on young people. The benefits are physical, emotional, social, and they help to develop a healthy appreciation of culture and the arts. Drama provides an excellent platform for exploring theoretical and practical aspects of all the subjects. The improvisation aspect of drama gives students opportunities for developing their communicative skills in authentic and dynamic situations. Drama has the potential of making the learning experience fun for the students and even memorable because it is interactive and visual. Creative drama

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will offer exercises in critical thinking and the chance for the students to be creative. Drama gives an excellent method for studying human nature and working in harmony. The play acting provides the opportunity for a healthy release of emotion in a safe setting which can work to relieve the tension of learning in a second language.

- Drama builds confidence.
- Drama helps concentration.
- Drama helps develop language & communication skills.
- Drama encourages children to co-operate.
- Drama supports numeracy skills
- Drama helps children to understand the world around them
- Drama develops emotional intelligence.
- Drama assists physical development.
- Drama develops creativity.
- Drama nurtures friendships
- Drama Brings Literature to Life
- Drama as a Powerful Teaching Tool.
- Drama Reveals Aspects of the Human Condition.
- To develop imagination capacity.
- Power of Transformation with Drama

Why students need study drama at high school?

- It will increase Students' self-esteem and confidence. They will make heaps of friends. They will learn the skills of listening, negotiating and communicating.
- Students will expand your cultural awareness. They will tour through a rich history of traditions and cultures. They will begin to know and appreciate that which is culturally and historically valuable.
- Students will learn empathy and identification. Drama opens up new dimensions of emotional experiences. By observing other people's creative processes and products, it can assist you in accessing emotions, along with understanding different ways of interpreting and understanding information. In drama we express ideas, observations and feelings by making choices about roles and/or characters
- It will increase your Students ability to think; creatively, imaginatively and divergently. They will learn how to think outside the square. Drama teaches students how to become

critical consumers, rather than just passive viewers. Students are expected to question and critique their own and others' processes and products.

- Students will develop higher order thinking skills. We can often be limited by our own attitudes and beliefs. Drama requires us to view things from multiple perspectives, inviting us to share control of a narrative between different players. This automatically widens our perspectives, allowing us to synthesise and evaluate information at a much higher level.
- Students will learn how to be creative. "Creativity, is an acquired behaviour – learnable, teachable, tangible and crucial to human development"
- Students will express your creativity in a variety of ways. In drama there is no right or wrong, creative play is encouraged and mistakes are often happy accidents. "Creative people do things. They make. They assemble. They put together. They make connections where connections were not previously apparent".
- Students will connect not only with yourself, but with other disciplines, cultures, traditions and most importantly with an audience.
- Students will learn how to work in a team effectively. Drama is full of games, or rather complex group dynamics and team building exercises (games sound more fun).
- Learning how to work collaboratively is a precious and important skill. Drama helps them to learn how to let go of what you want to say and respond to others' viewpoints or actions in a safe and fun environment.
- Students will learn about philosophical, ideological and political perspectives that different arts work represent (all drama is drawn from the world – we actually teach the basis of western civilization when we explore Ancient Greek Theatre. Pretty cool huh?).
- Students will walk away with an understanding of important aspects of our psychology – who we are, what we think, feel and act vs. what we say and do.
- Students will learn how to evaluate various art works and know what works, what doesn't and why.
- Students will learn how to speak in a more articulate manner, at the same time you will get to put on funny accents, or even sing or talk in babble.
- Students will learn how to use your body in ways that make people laugh.
- Students will learn how to make people cry.

- Students will begin to fully understand and experience the reality “that play is a natural way that children learn and develop”. Students will learn how to put on a theatre show or performance.
- You Students will become better writers and therefore increase your literacy and numeracy skills, through script writing, performance analysis and creative writing exercises.
- Students will expand their vocabulary and begin to use words like “hybrid” and “embody”.
- Students will learn how to memories things (learning lines requires practice, determination and advanced memory skills).
- Students will make meaning by undoing meaning... and they will understand what these kinds of expanded vocabulary.
- Students will learn about emotions and how to express them.
- Students will celebrate differences and diversities.
- Students will learn how to give feedback and take on board feedback. Drama teaches us how to ask questions that help make sense of learning.
- The two simple questions; ‘what worked’ and ‘what could be improved next time’ encourage students to offer constructive feedback and think critically and positively about their own and others’ performances.
- Students will get over your insecurities. In drama they have a right to be silly. One’s ability to laugh at our mistakes and ourselves is important in a business that can be tough and demanding. As students, it is sometimes difficult to take criticism of one’s work. In drama students have the chance to give and take feedback in a constructive way, not personal or hurtful. Students need to learn this and to be disciplined in their approach to a professional career but, at the same time, be willing to laugh and enjoy themselves in the process.
- Students will learn how to act with spontaneity and without self-consciousness. Remember though, this takes time and relies on how safe students feel with both teacher and other classmates. The ability to do this shows cooperation and communication in drama.
- Students will learn experientially (this means they will actually experience what they are learning).
- Students will learn about stagecraft and principles of design, by getting involved in set

designs or making models of sets (by the way, this is actually applied mathematics).

- Students will paint, make things and dress up in costumes and wigs.
- Students will get to play games (I mean, take part in team building exercises and complex group dynamics!).
- Students will be active. Drama is an active subject that requires you to get up and move most of the time. Students will learn how to tell a story and communicate with and without using words. Drama encourages us to communicate through different ways, whether it be through movement or speech or even just sounds. “Communication is at the roots of art”.
- Students will learn how to do things in slow motion. They will learn how to do things in fast motion. Students will learn to get in touch with your subconscious. Students will learn how to think on your feet. Students will learn how to focus and concentrate. Students will discover how to play with tension.
- Students will have fun. “The highest level of creativity unfolds through play.” – Albert Einstein .Students will maintain a sense of individuality and discover how to celebrate this.
- Students will demonstrate development of a personal style. They will build working relationships with other peers that may develop into long-lasting friendships and professional dynamics. They will have opportunities to become a great leader or the star of the high school production.
- Students will learn how to excel in public speaking/ presenting. Students will get to play around with multi/ hybrid arts. In drama popular culture can be used to explore kids’ lives and identities. Studies show that learning is made more meaningful and effective when students are given the opportunity to link their school activities to real-life experiences.
- Students will discover a process known as ‘reflection’. Reflection is not about solving problems, rather it is about noticing what is going on when you have a feeling or experience and suggesting possibilities that enrich our repertoire of understanding and influence our own art-making.
- Students will create plays from stimulus materials (such as picture books, music, film/ video). They will learn how to articulate what you want by working with others and taking on various roles, such as director.

- Students will get to engage in fun assessments. In drama these can include performances, Performance reviews, portfolios, journals, scripts and even making masks. They will learn how to make fun of yourself and not take yourself so seriously. They will find out how to create characters out of a simple body movement or picture.
- Students will discover how to do the impossible: fly, draw the world, and dissolve their body. Students will learn how to change your psychological and physiological state by simply changing the way that their body is positioned.
- Students will understand how to use heightened use of language, alliteration, hyperbole and may even speak in verse. They will learn all about comedy; such as pathos, satire, commedia art and physical comedy.
- Students will learn the rules of improvisation. Improvisation involves craft and skill, inviting students to think imaginatively and on their feet.
- One of the most important rules in improvisation is that you must accept all offers made by your partner, and not deny them. This allows a scene to be carried out to its full potential.
- Students will learn how to act in response to others, not just when they have lines to say. Students will learn how to push beyond their boundaries. They will learn how to create new work by using conventions from other styles. Drama is not just about creating; it is about “re-creating”. They will learn how to play with mood and atmosphere, through such things as music, to emotionally affect your audience.
- Students will learn how to create sounds capes they will learn how to transform objects, place, character through their body and imagination. They will get to see the bigger picture and on the flip side, explore the details. They will begin to understand the creative process. “Choices, alternatives, failures and doubt: The creative person works all of them out”. Students will get to (more than likely) go and see live performances. They will understand the difference between what it takes to be a professional artist.
- Students will learn about discipline, routine and structure without having to go to military school. The drama classroom can be like working in a professional theatre at times. For example, if they miss a performance, their absence affects the whole dynamics of the show.
- Students will be encouraged to be curious, open, present, inquisitive and funny. Students will learn how to research information online and offline and therefore gain the ability to evaluate the reliability and credibility of different information sources.

- Students will use technology (such as lights, video and sound) to create their own shows or school productions. “Technology can often and does enrich and extend the imagination of students.” They will learn how to rethink, reconsider, replace, refine, redo, reaffirm, reprocess, rewrite and reconceptualise. What better lesson could kids learn in coping with life than the importance of the “re” component?
- Students will learn how to be persistent and to learn from failures as well as successes. Students will learn to be aware. “People can become more and more creative by simply becoming more conscious of what it is that they do. The creative person sees the ordinary extraordinarily”. They will discover ways that they can make change, because “Creative people change the world”.

Conclusion:-

Drama has the potential to empower the students, give them many opportunities to have pride in their work, it teaches them responsibility, problem solving, management and directing proficiencies. The many activities of team work force students to develop organizational skills and to think on their feet. These are tools that can be used in all aspects of their lives. These skills will be useful in the future job market when the students need to work with others or even in the future job interview

Therefore, it makes sense that dramatic skills can help us become the person we want to be. In this way, drama has a wider reach than simply making us more fluent in a second language. It has the potential of making our lives better as we will be better understood and may help us become the people we want to be. Drama is all about how we present ourselves. If the student can communicate better, the more likely others will see him/her as he/she wishes to be seen. Therefore, the skills of drama can help the student become the person that he/she wants to be.

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